

Title:	Association between Face mask use and the Risk of Infection With SARS-CoV-2 in the Community – A cohort study
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ABSTRACT

Context:

Face masks have been recommended and/or mandated in many countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. We examine the association between face masks and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 in data obtained from a randomized trial on the effectiveness of using glasses in the community to reduce the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2.

Objectives:

Examine the association between face mask use and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 (self-reported)

Examine the association between face mask use and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 (notified) and respiratory infection based on self-report.

Study Design:

Cohort study.

Participants:

3717 adult members of the public who did not regularly wear glasses, had no symptoms of COVID-19, and did not have COVID-19 in the last 6 weeks.

Study Measures:

Self-reported COVID-19 as well as data on face mask use was collected from a survey of participants. Notified COVID-19 cases were collected from the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS).

1 BACKGROUND INFORMATION AND RATIONALE

1.1 Introduction

Public health authorities in many countries have recommended, mandated or both, the use of face masks to reduce the spread of COVID-19. This study examines the association between self-reported face mask use and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 in data obtained from a randomized trial on the effectiveness of using glasses in the community against the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2.

The literature on mask effectiveness for respiratory infection prevention is growing, but their use is still controversial, as demonstrated by the variation in recommendations on face mask use across countries and states.¹ Most studies are observational, and many find a negative association between wearing a mask and the risk of a COVID-19 infection,^{2,3} e.g. in their online survey, Xu et al found a manyfold increase in risk of infection among the participants who reported not wearing a face mask.⁴

Masks may have at least two types of effects on SARS-CoV-2 transmission. Wearing a mask by an infected individual may prevent spread from infected people to others (source control). Wearing a mask may also protect the wearers (protective effect).⁵

In this study we revisit the association between use of face masks and the protection against infection from COVID-19. We examine this relationship by using already collected data from a trial we conducted February to April 2022, of wearing glasses to reduce viral transmission⁶. We do not claim that we will be able to identify the causal effect of wearing face masks on the risk of COVID-19, but our results may give an indication of the direction of such an effect, if we can reasonably assume that we adjust for all relevant confounders.

2 STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary objective is to examine the association between face mask use and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 (self-reported) adjusted for all observable confounding variables.

Examine the association between face mask use and the risk of infection with SARS-CoV-2 (notified) and respiratory infection based on self-report adjusted for all observable confounding variables.

3 STUDY POPULATION

The following eligibility requirements had to be met by all trial participants:

1. at least 18 years of age
 2. did not regularly wear glasses
 3. owned or could borrow glasses that they could use (e.g., sunglasses)
 4. had not contracted COVID-19 in the 6 weeks prior to participation
 5. did not have COVID-19 symptoms when providing consent
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6. willing to be randomly assigned to wear or not wear glasses outside their home when close to others for a 2-week period
 7. provided informed consent.

4 DATA SOURCES

We used data that we had already collected for our trial of wearing glasses against transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in the community⁷. The trial data stemmed from the following sources:

4.1.1 End of follow-up survey

- Use of face masks during the follow-up period
- Use of contact lenses
- Use of glasses during the follow-up period
- Use of public transportation during the follow-up period
- Testing for COVID-19 during the follow-up period
- Test result for COVID-19 during the follow-up period
- Test date for COVID-19

Details on the specific survey items is found in appendix 1.

4.1.2 Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS)

- Date of positive COVID-19 test

4.1.3 Norwegian Immunisation Registry SYSVAK

- Date of vaccination for a COVID-19 vaccine

4.1.4 Identification number

- Date of birth
- Sex

5 DESIGN

We will analyse the data from the randomised trial as a cohort study of the effect of face mask use on the risk of infection. We will redistribute the participants from the two trials groups (glass use or no use) into three groups based on their retrospective report of the level of face mask use during the study period.

We will estimate crude and adjusted models where we examine how face mask use affects the risk of infection with COVID-19 or other respiratory infections.

5.1 Primary and Secondary Endpoints

The primary outcome is a positive COVID-19 test (self-reported - days 1-17 of the study period).

Secondary outcomes includes (1) a positive COVID-19 test result (notified; days 1-17 of study period) and (2) an episode of respiratory infection (self-reported symptoms; days 1-17

of study period), defined as having 1 respiratory symptom (stuffed or runny nose, sore throat, cough, sneezing, or heavy breathing) and fever or 1 respiratory symptom and at least 2 more symptoms (body ache, muscular pain, fatigue, reduced appetite, stomach pain, headache, and/or loss of smell).

5.2 Face mask use

Survey respondents reported on face mask use by selecting one of the following 6 responses on the question “How often over the last two weeks have you used a face mask when you have been close to others outside your home?”

- (1) Always
- (2) Almost always (at least 75% of the time)
- (3) Often (50-75% of the time)
- (4) Sometimes (25-50 % of the time)
- (5) A few times (up to 25% of the time)
- (6) Never (0% of the time)

Owing to few responses for some of the categories, in the analysis we will combine the response categories into:

- (1) Always / almost always
- (2) Often / sometimes
- (3) Almost never / never

5.3 Potential biases

Participants were not randomised to wear or not to wear a face mask. They were not encouraged to wear face masks nor informed about or provided with face masks.

During the study period, the recommendation to wear a face mask was changed. Pre 12th February 2022, face mask use was mandated when it was not possible to retain 1 meter distance in shops, shopping malls, restaurants, public transport, taxis and inside public venues. The mandate was also applied to employees unless physical barriers were used.

From the 12th of February and onwards some of participants' use of face masks during the study period may well be a result of their own choice based perhaps on their evaluation of their own risk and the effectiveness of face masks.

We believe that there may also be some factors that may confound the relationship between face mask use and the endpoints in the study:

Firstly, participants in some professions that increase the likelihood of exposure and infection, may have chosen to wear masks more often, for instance shop workers, bartenders or taxi drivers. This higher risk may have masked the effect of face masking.

Secondly, participants with risk factors for severe COVID-19 may have chosen to wear masks more often to protect themselves. This higher risk of symptomatic or more severe COVID-19, and thus higher risk of diagnosis, may have masked the effect of face masking.

Thirdly, some health-conscious participants may have chosen to wear masks because they do a lot to avoid being infected. Thus, they may have avoided being infected because of other measures, not because of face masking.

Because of these and other potential unmeasured confounding, we will take care not to interpret the results as causal relationships between face mask use and infection risk.

5.4 Statistical Methods

We will first measure the cumulative incidence proportion (“attack rate” or risk) of each of the outcomes in each of the three groups defined by frequency of mask use.

We will then compute risk ratios (RR) and adjusted risk ratios (ARR) using binomial generalized linear models with log link function⁸. If these fail to converge we will use robust Poisson regression models.⁹ Reporting “Almost never” / ”never” having used face masks will be set as the reference level.

We will compute risk differences (RD) and adjusted risk differences (ARD) using generalized linear models with a Gaussian distribution and identity link function, with robust standard errors⁸. Reporting “Almost never” / “never” having used face masks will be set as the reference level.

In the adjusted models we will adjust for:

- Age (continuous + quadratic term)
- Sex
- Using contact lenses
- Having used glasses (Always / almost always; Often / sometimes; Almost never / never)
- Use of public transportation
- Vaccination status (0,1,2,3+ doses)
- The share of the follow-up time where face mask use was mandatory

The table with the main results for the primary outcome will then look like this (with fictive numbers):

Exposure group	Infected / Total	Risk (95 % CI)	Risk ratio (95 % CI)	Adjusted risk ratio (95 % CI)
Almost never / Never	60 / 1100	5.5 % (4.2 – 6.9)	Referent	Referent

Sometimes / Often	45 / 1075	4.2 % (3.1 – 5.5)	0.77 (0.53 – 1.1)	0.72 (0.50 – 1.1)
Almost always / Always	25 / 1025	2.4 % (1.6 – 3.5)	0.45 (0.28 – 0.71)	0.47 (0.29 – 0.75)

Similar tables will be made for the secondary outcomes.

Sensitivity analysis

We will conduct two sensitivity analysis:

1. Stratification by whether facemask was mandatory in part of the follow-up period or not
2. Fractional polynomials to model time-varying differences in baseline risk of infection. will consider fractional polynomials of maximum degree 2, with powers restricted to the set [5 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3]. We will choose among models using the closed testing procedure which is the default approach of the mfp package¹⁰ in R.

6 STUDY ADMINISTRATION

6.1 Regulatory and Ethical Considerations

Our trial of wearing glasses to reduce viral transmission received ethical approval by the Regional Ethics Committee of South-East Norway.

6.2 Informed Consent/Assent

Informed consent was obtained from participants during the original trial.⁶

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APPENDIX
Questionnaire (translated from Norwegian)

Questions	Type of response	Options
1. Do you wear contact lenses?	Categories	Yes, /No
2. How often over the last two weeks have you been using glasses (reading glasses, sunglasses, sports glasses etc.) when you have been close to others outside your home?	Categories	Always/Almost always (at least 75% of the time)/ Often (50-75% of the time)/Sometimes (25-50 % of the time)/A few times (up to 25% of the time)/Never (0% of the time)
3. How often over the last two weeks have you used a face mask when you have been close to others outside your home?	Categories	Always/Almost always (at least 75% of the time)/ Often (50-75% of the time)/Sometimes (25-50 % of the time)/A few times (up to 25% of the time)/Never (0% of the time)
3. Do you normally use public transportation (bus, train, tram, metro, ferry, taxi) to and from work/study place?	Categories	Yes/No
4. Have you experienced one of the following symptoms since taking part in the study?	Categories	Headache/Fever/Clogged nose or runny nose/ Reduced sense of smell/Reduced appetite/ Sore throat /Cough/ Sneezing/Body aches/ Muscle pain/Fatigue, lethargy/Heavy breathing/Abdominal pain
5. Have you taken a COVID-19 over the last two weeks (self-test/test at testing facility)?	Categories	Yes, both self-test and at testing facility/Yes, but only a test station/Yes, but only self-test/No

7. What was the test result?	Categories	Positive/Negative/Unsure
8. When did you take the test?	Date	
9. Have you needed any medical care after you took part in the study?	Categories	Yes/No
Item 10-11 if response "Yes" on item 9		
10. Did you need for medical care due to respiratory symptoms?	Categories	Yes/No
11. Did you need for medical care due to injuries?	Categories	Yes/No
12. Have you had any negative experiences from participating in this study?	Categories	Yes/No
Item 13 if response "Yes" on item 12		
13. Please describe what those experiences were	Free text	